

Effect of different tilt angles on the performance of the different PV panels in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of varying tilt angles on the performance of crystalline silicon (c-Si) and copper indium diselenide (CIS) photovoltaic (PV) panels in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso. Located in West Africa, Burkina Faso possesses significant solar energy potential, yet faces considerable challenges in terms of energy access, particularly in rural regions. This research focuses on 3 kW power PV systems, employing the PVGIS (Photovoltaic Geographical Information System) software and the SARAH solar radiation database to conduct simulations at different tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) with a fixed south-facing orientation (azimuth angle of 0°). The 3 kWp system size was selected as a scalable option suitable for meeting the energy needs of a typical household or small business in the area, and appropriate for off-grid applications. Using typical meteorological year (TMY) data for Pouytenga, monthly average simulations were carried out. Key performance indicators, including annual energy yield (kWh), average monthly energy production (kWh/month), performance ratio (PR), and capacity factor (CF), were analyzed. The results enable the determination of the optimal tilt angle for both c-Si and CIS PV technologies, as well as a comparison of their performance at different tilt angles. This study provides practical insights for optimizing the design and installation of 3 kW power PV systems in Pouytenga and other regions with similar climatic conditions, ultimately contributing to more effective utilization of solar energy and improved energy access.

1. Introduction

Solar energy is a clean, abundant, and sustainable energy source that plays an increasingly important role in meeting global energy demand and combating climate change. Photovoltaic (PV) technologies, in particular, are widely used in both grid-connected and off-grid systems due to their ability to directly convert sunlight into electricity [1-2]. The performance of PV systems is affected by various factors, primarily solar radiation, temperature, shading, panel tilt, and orientation [3-4]. Among these factors, the tilt angle at which PV panels are installed is an optimizable design parameter that directly affects the amount of solar radiation received by the panel surface and, consequently, energy production [5].

This study was conducted in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso, a town located in the sub-Saharan region of West Africa, which has high solar energy potential but low electricity access rates. As of 2021, the electricity access rate in Burkina Faso was 22.5%, dropping below 5% in rural areas [6]. The majority of the country's energy needs are met by traditional biomass sources, leading to negative environmental and socio-economic impacts such as deforestation, air pollution, and health problems [7]. In this context, off-grid solar energy systems offer a promising solution for increasing electricity access, improving quality of life, and supporting sustainable development in rural areas of Burkina Faso [8].

The literature frequently emphasizes the importance of panel tilt angle among the factors influencing the performance of PV systems [1-4]. The optimal tilt angle maximizes the amount of solar radiation incident on the panel surface, thereby increasing energy production. However, the optimal tilt angle varies depending on geographic location, season, and even the PV technology used. Accurate determination of solar radiation quantity and spectral distribution is critical for accurate performance prediction and optimization of PV systems [9-11]. Therefore, obtaining and modeling solar radiation data with high accuracy for different regions and climatic conditions is of great importance in PV system design and site selection. Various studies have attempted to determine optimal tilt angles for different regions and climatic conditions, and some have demonstrated the benefits of seasonal tilt angle adjustment [12-17]. Furthermore, some studies have made comparative examinations on c-Si and CIS panels [18]. There are also studies where they examine fixed and tracking systems [19]. Additionally, studies conducted in regions at different latitudes demonstrate the importance of tilt angle optimization [20]. Research on how to make tilt angle adjustments in the most appropriate way, maintains its currency [21]. However, comprehensive studies that compare both crystalline silicon (c-Si) and copper indium diselenide (CIS) thin-film technologies, consider different system sizes, and analyze monthly energy production data to determine the optimal tilt angle are limited, particularly for specific locations such as Pouytenga, Burkina Faso.

This study aims to address this gap and provide scientifically based and practically applicable recommendations for tilt angle optimization in 3 kW powered PV systems for Pouytenga. The 3 kW powered system size was considered a scalable option that can meet the basic electricity needs (lighting, television, radio, phone charging, small appliances, and potentially a small refrigerator) of a typical household or small business in the region, while also accommodating potential future increases in energy demand. To this end, the impact of different tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) on the energy production of two different PV panel technologies (c-Si and CIS) was investigated using the PVGIS (Photovoltaic Geographical Information System) software, developed by the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC), and the SARA solar radiation database.

This study distinguishes itself from similar studies in the literature by its focus on a specific geographical region, Pouytenga, its comparative analysis of c-Si and CIS technologies, and its examination of not only annual but also monthly energy production data to reveal seasonal trends. The findings will contribute to optimizing the design and installation of 3 kW power PV systems in Pouytenga and other sub-Saharan African regions with similar climatic conditions, thereby increasing energy efficiency and enabling more effective utilization of solar energy.

2. Material and Method

This study aims to quantitatively evaluate the impact of varying tilt angles on the performance of 3 kW nominal power c-Si and CIS PV panels in the Pouytenga region of Burkina Faso. To achieve this, simulations were performed using the PVGIS software [22] and the SARA solar radiation database.

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in the town of Pouytenga, located in the Koupéla Department of the Centre-Est Region of Burkina Faso. Pouytenga is situated at coordinates 12.2525° N latitude and 0.426944° W longitude, at an elevation of 314 meters above sea level. The location of Pouytenga within Burkina Faso is illustrated in [Figure 1](#). The region experiences a savanna climate, characterized by consistently high temperatures throughout the year and distinct dry and rainy seasons.

Figure 1. Location of Pouytenga within Burkina Faso (PVGIS).

[Table 1](#) presents the monthly average, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation of temperature values (°C) for Pouytenga for the period 2009-2023. As shown, the annual average temperature is approximately 28.9 °C. The hottest months are April and May, with average temperatures of 33.3 °C and 32.4 °C, respectively, while the coolest months are determined to be January, with an average of 26.0 °C, followed by August and December both averaging 26.1 °C. High temperatures are a significant factor negatively impacting PV panel efficiency.

Table 1. Monthly temperature values (°C) for Pouytenga (2009-2023, PVGIS-SARAH).

Month	Average Temperature (°C)	Minimum Temperature (°C)	Maximum Temperature (°C)	Standard Deviation (°C)
January	26.0	24.7	27.3	0.74
February	28.6	26.1	30.2	1.05
March	31.9	30.9	32.6	0.57
April	33.3	32.0	34.2	0.65
May	32.4	30.6	33.9	0.83
June	30.0	29.0	31.1	0.66
July	27.5	26.2	28.6	0.69
August	26.1	25.4	26.7	0.49
September	26.8	25.6	27.8	0.61
October	28.6	27.7	29.6	0.62
November	28.4	27.1	29.7	0.88
December	26.1	23.9	28.9	1.17

Table 2 presents the monthly average, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation of global horizontal irradiation (GHI) values (kWh/m²/month) for Pouytenga for the period 2009-2023. The annual average GHI is 5.71 kWh/m²/day, indicating the region's high solar energy potential. The highest GHI values are observed in March (213.55 kWh/m²/month) and April (206.39 kWh/m²/month), while the lowest values are observed in August (170.30 kWh/m²/month) and July (177.86 kWh/m²/month). Table 3 presents the monthly average diffuse/global radiation rate for Pouytenga.

Table 2. Monthly GHI Values for Pouytenga (PVGIS-SARAH, 2009-2023).

Month	Average GHI (kWh/m ² /month)	Minimum GHI (kWh/m ² /month)	Maximum GHI (kWh/m ² /month)	Standard Deviation (kWh/m ² /month)
January	189.90	160.54	197.08	9.57
February	187.75	176.81	199.84	6.99
March	213.55	193.38	225.57	8.56
April	206.39	193.43	223.15	7.66
May	206.11	199.80	220.85	5.46
June	186.04	172.67	193.84	6.94
July	177.86	164.82	185.21	5.87
August	170.30	156.31	179.64	6.83
September	176.63	150.03	190.25	9.34
October	194.73	186.15	208.52	6.60
November	186.41	179.82	193.59	3.80
December	185.27	174.64	190.73	4.54
Yearly Average	5.71 kWh/m ² /day			

Table 3. Monthly Diffuse/Global Radiation Rate for Pouytenga (PVGIS-SARAH, 2009-2023).

Month	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation
January	0.27	0.25	0.34	0.02
February	0.28	0.26	0.33	0.02
March	0.35	0.33	0.36	0.01
April	0.36	0.31	0.39	0.02
May	0.36	0.33	0.39	0.02
June	0.41	0.35	0.46	0.03
July	0.44	0.4	0.48	0.02
August	0.47	0.43	0.51	0.02
September	0.38	0.27	0.48	0.05
October	0.32	0.29	0.36	0.02
November	0.28	0.25	0.32	0.02
December	0.27	0.23	0.29	0.02

PV system performance simulations were conducted using PVGIS, a web-based and freely available tool developed by the European Commission JRC [22].

In this study, the PVGIS-SARAH2 (Surface Solar Radiation Data Set - Heliosat) database was utilized for solar radiation, temperature, and diffuse-to-global radiation ratio data. PVGIS-SARAH2 is a high-resolution dataset derived using the Heliosat method from the visible channel data of Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) satellites. It has a spatial resolution of 0.05° x 0.05° (approximately 5 km) and a temporal resolution of 30 minutes [9-10]. The SARAH2 dataset covers the period from 2005 to 2020. PVGIS automatically generates Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) data for the specified location, providing a dataset that represents long-term average climate conditions.

To evaluate the solar energy potential of the Pouytenga region under different scenarios, PVGIS simulations employed two distinct PV panel technologies: c-Si and CIS. Default module parameters from the PVGIS software were used for both technologies. The system size was set at 3 kWp, reflecting the likely energy needs of households and small businesses in a rural area. The tilt angle, a crucial factor influencing PV panel performance, was investigated at four different values: 0° (horizontal), 10°, 20°, and 30°. In all simulations, the azimuth angle of the

panels was set to 0° (south-facing) to ensure maximum solar irradiance collection in the Northern Hemisphere. Furthermore, system losses, encompassing temperature effects, cable losses, inverter inefficiency, soiling, and other potential losses, were assumed to be 14%, the default value in the PVGIS software. The mounting configuration was selected as 'free-standing,' representing a typical ground-mounted installation. Based on these parameters, monthly average energy production simulations were conducted for a total of 8 different scenarios (2 PV technologies × 4 tilt angles).

Performance parameters were calculated using the average monthly electricity production from the defined system (E_m), the average monthly sum of global irradiation per square meter received by the modules of the given system ($H_{(i),m}$), and annual total energy production (E_y) values obtained from the PVGIS simulations. The Performance Ratio (PR), a dimensionless metric, represents the actual efficiency of a PV system after accounting for losses. PR is widely used to compare the performance of PV systems independently of system size, location, and climatic conditions [23]. In this study, the PR value was calculated using Equation 1 below:

$$PR = \left(\frac{E_y}{(1000P_0)} \right) \div \left(\frac{H_{(i),y}}{1000} \right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, E_y represents the annual energy production of the PV system (in kWh), P_0 represents the nominal power of the PV system (in kW). $H_{(i),y}$ represents the annual total in-plane solar irradiation incident on the PV panel surface (in kWh/m²). The total yearly in-plane solar irradiation was obtained by summing the monthly in-plane solar irradiation values ($H_{(i),m}$) from PVGIS.

The Capacity Factor (CF) is the ratio of the actual energy produced by a PV system over a specific period (one year in this study) to the maximum possible energy that could have been produced if the system operated continuously at its nominal power during the same period. Expressed as a percentage (%), the CF indicates how closely a PV power plant operates to its full capacity throughout the year and is used to evaluate the performance of an energy production facility. In this study, the CF value was calculated using Equation 2:

$$CF = \left(\frac{E_y}{(P_0 \times 8760)} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The Specific Yield (SY) represents the annual energy produced per unit of installed capacity (kW) of a PV system, expressed in kWh/kW. It is a metric used to compare the performance of PV systems with different installed capacities [24]. In this study, the SY value was calculated using Equation 3:

$$SY = \frac{E_y}{P_0} \quad (3)$$

The effects of varying tilt angles on the performance of the PV panels were compared and analyzed using the performance parameters defined above (PR, CF, and SY). These parameters provide a comprehensive assessment of system performance, accounting for energy production, efficiency, and utilization of installed capacity. The results of these analyses, including detailed comparisons between c-Si and CIS technologies and across the different tilt angles, are presented in the form of tables and figures.

3. Results

This section presents the results of simulations conducted using the PVGIS software and the PVGIS-SARAH database to evaluate the performance of 3 kW nominal power c-Si and CIS PV systems at different tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso. The simulations provide detailed monthly and annual data on

energy production, allowing for a comprehensive comparison of the two PV technologies under varying installation conditions.

3.1. Performance of c-Si PV Systems

This section presents the performance results for the 3 kW powered c-Si PV systems in Pouytenga. Table 4 shows the monthly average energy production, in-plane solar irradiation, and the standard deviation of the monthly electricity production due to year-to-year variation (SD_m) for c-Si systems at different tilt angles (0° , 10° , 20° , and 30°).

Table 4. E_m , $H_{(i),m}$ and SD_m values for 3 kW powered c-Si PV systems in Pouytenga.

MONTHS	E_m (kWh)				$H_{(i),m}$ (kWh/m ²)				SD_m (kWh)			
	Tilt Angle				Tilt Angle				Tilt Angle			
	0	10	20	30	0	10	20	30	0	10	20	30
January	422.4	468.3	502.6	524.9	189.6	210.2	225.9	236.1	18.7	21.4	23.5	25
February	412.5	440.7	459.0	466.9	189.1	202.4	211.1	214.7	15.6	17.2	18.3	18.9
March	458.5	469.3	470.6	462.1	215.0	220.6	221.3	217.1	13.6	14.3	14.5	14.5
April	441.4	435.8	421.4	398.2	207.7	205.3	198.4	187.4	16.8	16.5	15.7	14.5
May	441.8	424.3	398.1	363.2	205.5	197.5	185.3	169.4	16.3	15.4	14.3	12.7
June	406.2	385.7	357.5	321.6	185.9	176.7	164.0	148.2	13.7	12.5	10.8	8.9
July	397.9	380.2	355.2	322.6	179.0	171.2	160.3	146.2	11.9	11.3	10.2	9.1
August	379.8	371.4	356.0	333.6	169.1	165.5	158.8	149.0	13.7	13.3	12.6	11.6
September	393.3	396.5	391.8	379.3	177.5	179.2	177.2	171.4	18.7	19.1	19	18.4
October	430.3	451.5	463.0	464.5	197.1	207.3	212.9	213.5	12.7	13.9	14.7	15.1
November	406.9	445.4	473.1	489.9	186.6	204.6	217.8	225.7	9.2	10.8	12	12.8
December	413.9	464.9	504.0	530.7	186.2	209.0	226.9	239.2	6.3	7.6	8.8	9.8

Figure 2 presents a comparison of the annual total energy production for 3 kW powered c-Si systems in Pouytenga at various tilt angles (0° , 10° , 20° , and 30°). The calculated annual energy yields were 5005.01 kWh at 0° , 5133.90 kWh at 10° , 5152.22 kWh at 20° , and 5057.52 kWh at 30° . While all tilt angles resulted in relatively similar energy yields, the 20° tilt angle produced the highest annual energy, exceeding the output of the 0° (horizontal) configuration by approximately 3%.

Figure 2. Comparison of annual total energy production of 3 kW powered c-Si systems at different tilt angles.

Figure 3 presents the monthly average energy production for 3 kW powered c-Si systems in Pouytenga, illustrating the impact of varying tilt angles (0° , 10° , 20° , and 30°). A distinct seasonal trend is evident across all

tilt configurations, characterized by peak energy production in March and April, and a trough in July and August. This pattern closely mirrors the seasonal variations in the monthly average GHI shown in Table 2. Notably, while the trend is consistent, the magnitude of energy production differs significantly between tilt angles. For instance, in March, the 20° tilt angle yields the highest energy production, whereas in August, the 0° tilt exhibits a slightly higher output than other angles. This suggests a complex interaction between solar irradiance, angle of incidence, and potentially, temperature effects throughout the year.

Figure 3. Comparison of monthly total energy production of 3 kW powered c-Si systems at different tilt angles.

3.2. Performance of CIS PV Systems

This section focuses on the performance results for the 3 kW powered CIS PV systems installed in Pouytenga. Table 5 provides a detailed overview of the monthly average energy production (E_m), the average monthly in-plane solar irradiation ($H_{(i),m}$), and the standard deviation of the monthly energy production (SD_m) for these CIS systems across the various tilt angles studied (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°).

Table 5. E_m , $H_{(i),m}$ and SD_m values for 3 kW powered CSI PV systems in Pouytenga.

MONTHS	E_m (kWh)				$H_{(i),m}$ (kWh/m ²)				SD_m (kWh)			
	Tilt Angle				Tilt Angle				Tilt Angle			
	0	10	20	30	0	10	20	30	0	10	20	30
January	420.1	465.5	499.2	521.1	189.6	210.2	225.9	236.1	18.6	21.3	23.3	24.8
February	412.6	440.6	458.5	466.4	189.1	202.4	211.1	214.7	15.3	16.8	17.9	18.4
March	459.8	470.4	471.6	463.3	215.0	220.6	221.3	217.1	13.6	14.2	14.5	14.4
April	442.3	436.6	422.3	398.2	207.7	205.3	198.4	187.4	16.9	16.5	15.8	14.5
May	442.6	425.0	400.2	363.2	205.5	197.5	185.3	169.4	16.4	15.6	14.4	12.7
June	405.2	385.7	356.2	319.8	185.9	176.7	164.0	148.2	13.9	12.5	10.8	9.1
July	394.6	380.2	353.1	319.2	179.0	171.2	160.3	146.2	12.0	11.3	10.2	9.2
August	374.7	366.3	351.1	328.7	169.1	165.5	158.8	149.0	13.8	13.4	12.7	11.7
September	389.8	392.9	388.3	375.8	177.5	179.2	177.2	171.4	18.9	19.3	19.2	18.4
October	428.4	449.5	460.9	462.4	197.1	207.3	212.9	213.5	12.9	14.1	14.9	15.1
November	405.9	444.1	471.5	488.1	186.6	204.6	217.8	225.7	8.9	10.4	11.6	12.4
December	411.2	461.8	499.1	530.7	186.2	209.0	226.9	239.2	6.2	7.5	8.8	9.6

Figure 4 compares the annual total energy production for 3 kW powered CIS systems in Pouytenga across the investigated tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°). The annual energy values were 4987.26 kWh at 0°, 5114.38 kWh at

10°, 5130.47 kWh at 20°, and 5033.75 kWh at 30°. While the differences in annual energy production between the various tilt angles are relatively small, the results indicate that a 20° tilt angle provides the highest annual yield for 3 kWp CIS systems in Pouytenga.

Figure 4. Comparison of annual total energy production of 3 kW powered CSI systems at different tilt angles.

Figure 5 presents the monthly average energy production for 3 kW powered CIS systems in Pouytenga, demonstrating the influence of different tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) on system output. A clear seasonal trend is observed for all tilt angles, characterized by peaks in energy production during January, March, November, and December. Conversely, the months of June, July, and August exhibit the lowest energy production. This seasonal pattern aligns with the variations in monthly average GHI (Table 2) and the diffuse-to-global radiation ratio (Table 3). Specifically, the diminished energy production observed in July and August can be attributed to the increased diffuse radiation ratio and corresponding lower GHI values during this period. Although the effect of tilt angle varies from month to month, the 20° tilt generally exhibits energy production levels that are either higher than or comparable to those of the other tested angles throughout much of the year.

Figure 5. Comparison of monthly total energy production of 3 kW powered CSI systems at different tilt angles.

Building upon the monthly energy production data presented in the previous tables, [Table 6](#) summarizes the key annual performance parameters for both 3 kW powered c-Si and CIS photovoltaic systems in Pouytenga. The table allows for a direct comparison of annual energy production values (kWh), performance ratio (PR, %), capacity factor (CF, %), and specific yield (kWh/kWp) across the investigated tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°).

Table 6. Performance comparison of 3 kWp c-Si and CIS PV systems in Pouytenga.

PV Technology	Tilt Angle (°)	Annual Energy Product (kWh)	Performance Ratio (PR) (%)	Capacity Factor (CF) (%)	Specific Yield (SY) (kWh/kW)
c-Si	0	5005.01	73.01	19.05	1668.34
c-Si	10	5133.9	72.85	19.54	1711.3
c-Si	20	5152.22	72.77	19.61	1717.41
c-Si	30	5057.52	72.73	19.24	1685.84
CIS	0	4987.26	72.66	18.98	1662.42
CIS	10	5114.38	72.57	19.46	1704.79
CIS	20	5130.47	72.46	19.52	1710.16
CIS	30	5033.75	72.39	19.15	1677.92

Table 6 provides a comparison of the annual performance parameters for 3 kW powered c-Si and CIS PV systems at various tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) in Pouytenga. As the table indicates, annual energy production varies with tilt angle for both PV technologies. The highest annual energy production for both c-Si and CIS systems was achieved at a 20° tilt angle. The c-Si system produced 5152.22 kWh at 20°, while the CIS system produced 5130.47 kWh at the same angle. This suggests that, for Pouytenga, a 20° tilt angle provides the best overall alignment with the angle of incidence of solar radiation and the variation in daylight hours throughout the year.

Comparing the two technologies, the difference in annual energy production is minimal. At the optimal 20° tilt, the c-Si system produced only 0.4% more energy than the CIS system. However, a review of the PR values reveals that c-Si systems consistently exhibit slightly higher PR values across all tilt angles. This could indicate that, under the default system loss assumptions used in PVGIS (14%), c-Si panels are marginally more efficient in Pouytenga's conditions. It is important to emphasize, however, that this difference is not substantial, and both technologies demonstrate comparable performance.

As expected, the 0° (horizontal) tilt angle resulted in the lowest annual energy production for both technologies, due to the non-perpendicular incidence of solar radiation for a significant portion of the year. As the tilt angle increased to 10° and 20°, annual energy production also increased. However, at a 30° tilt, a slight decrease in energy production was observed. This suggests that a 30° tilt is steeper than optimal for Pouytenga's latitude (approximately 12° N), leading to lower angles of incidence for solar radiation during certain parts of the year.

The specific yield values (kWh/kW) are very close for both technologies and across all tilt angles. This confirms that, as expected, system size (3 kW powered) has a proportional impact on energy production, but does not significantly alter the efficiency per unit of installed capacity.

As illustrated in [Figure 3](#) and [Figure 5](#), energy production for both technologies and all tilt angles exhibits pronounced seasonal fluctuations. Peak production generally occurs during March-April and October-November, periods characterized by more direct solar irradiance and longer daylight hours. Conversely, the lowest production values are observed during July-August, coinciding with the rainy season and a higher diffuse-to-global radiation ratio (see [Table 3](#)). This observation partially contradicts the generally accepted notion that CIS technology performs better under diffuse radiation conditions. Further, a more detailed investigation, taking into account local climatic conditions (e.g., soiling), is warranted to explain this discrepancy.

4. Discussion

This study investigated the performance of 3 kW powered c-Si and CIS PV systems at different tilt angles (0°, 10°, 20°, and 30°) in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso, using the PVGIS software and SARA solar radiation database. The findings demonstrate that both tilt angle and PV technology have a significant impact on energy production.

For both PV technologies, the optimum tilt angle that maximized annual total energy production was determined to be 20° (Table 4 and Table 5). This result aligns with expectations, given Pouytenga's latitude (approximately 12° N). Generally, the optimal tilt angle for fixed-tilt PV systems is close to or slightly higher than the latitude of the location [3-4]. However, the influence of tilt angle on energy production exhibits seasonal variations, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 5. Specifically, during the summer months (June-August), when the diffuse radiation ratio is high (Table 3), lower tilt angles (0° and 10°) showed slightly better performance. This can be attributed to the ability of panels with lower tilt angles to more effectively capture diffuse radiation. Conversely, during the winter months, when the sun's rays are at a lower angle, higher tilt angles (20° and 30°) were found to be more advantageous.

When comparing the annual energy production of c-Si and CIS PV systems at the optimum tilt angle of 20°, c-Si systems produced marginally more energy (5152.22 kWh) than CIS systems (5130.47 kWh), a difference of only 0.4% (Table 3 and Table 5). The PR values also indicate that c-Si systems are slightly more efficient under the default system loss assumptions (14%) used in PVGIS. However, it is important to emphasize that this difference is minimal, and both technologies exhibit comparable performance in Pouytenga. The literature suggests that CIS thin-film panels may perform better under high temperatures and diffuse radiation conditions [23]. While this study observed relatively better performance of CIS panels during July and August (months with high diffuse radiation ratios and high temperatures), this did not translate into a significant difference in overall annual energy production.

The PR values obtained for both technologies (around 72-73%) fall within the expected range for well-designed and installed PV systems [25]. The CF values (around 19%) reflect Pouytenga's solar resource, but it should be noted that CF can be lower in off-grid systems due to factors such as battery charge/discharge cycles and other system losses not fully captured in the PVGIS simulations. The SY values (1662-1717 kWh/kW) were very close for both technologies, confirming that system size (3 kW powered) proportionally impacts energy production but does not significantly alter efficiency (energy production per unit of power).

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the default system loss value (14%) and default module parameters used in PVGIS may not perfectly represent the actual installation conditions in Pouytenga. Factors such as dust accumulation, soiling, shading, and local microclimate conditions (e.g., wind speed) could affect PV system performance differently than estimated by PVGIS. Furthermore, the PVGIS-SARA database, being satellite-derived, may contain some inherent uncertainties compared to ground-based measurements [9].

Future studies could involve installing a real PV system in Pouytenga to collect experimental data on different tilt angles and PV technologies, aiding in PVGIS model validation and calibration. Additionally, economic analyses could assess cost-effectiveness, while research on battery storage options could explore their impact on performance and cost. Lastly, studies on the socio-economic effects of PV systems, such as energy access, household income, and job creation, would be valuable.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that a tilt angle of approximately 20° is optimal for 3 kW powered PV systems in Pouytenga, Burkina Faso, for both c-Si and CIS technologies. Both technologies exhibit high energy production potential in this region, with c-Si showing a marginally higher annual yield and PR in the simulations. These results provide valuable guidance for the design and installation of PV systems in Pouytenga and similar climates, contributing to more effective utilization of solar energy and increased energy access, especially in off-grid, rural electrification projects.

However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The simulations relied on PVGIS default system loss parameters and module characteristics, which may not perfectly reflect real-world installation conditions in Pouytenga. Factors such as dust accumulation, soiling, shading from nearby objects, and grid quality (if applicable) could influence system performance differently.

Future work should focus on collecting in-situ performance data from operational PV systems in Pouytenga, using various tilt angles and both c-Si and CIS technologies. This empirical data would allow for validation and calibration of the PVGIS model, improving its accuracy for local conditions. Furthermore, a comprehensive economic analysis, incorporating local costs and electricity tariffs, is recommended to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of different system configurations. Finally, investigations into the socio-economic impact of PV system deployment, including increased energy access, income generation, and job creation, would provide a more holistic understanding of the benefits of solar energy in this region.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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